

Quality Management as a key strategy for happiness in federation-based sport

Gestión de calidad como estrategia clave de la felicidad en el deporte federado

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Abstract

The relationship between sport and happiness has been proven on many occasions. On this way, physical sport gives sportspeople positive feelings which are all related to the term happiness. Therefore, based on the fact that taking part in sports increases happiness, the main objective of this study is to determine which variables have the greatest influence on sportspeople's happiness, focusing specifically on federation members. One of the new developments in this study is that the results may help members of the Governing Boards of these federations to take better decisions and contribute more to the happiness of sportspeople who are federation members. The main variables mentioned in the literature as having a positive influence on happiness are perceived quality and satisfaction. There are also studies that confirm the influence of trust and social relationships on happiness. The empirical research has used primary data from a survey of 601 members of the Spanish regional federations, specifically in karate. The results confirm all the hypotheses advances in this study. Thus, as indicated by the literature reviewed, the four variables studied (perceived quality and satisfaction, trust and social relationships) all exert significant positive influence on levels of happiness.

Resumen

La relación entre el deporte y la felicidad es un hecho probado en multitud de ocasiones. El ejercicio físico aporta al deportista diversas sensaciones positivas, todas ellas muy relacionadas con el término felicidad. Por tanto, partiendo del hecho de que la práctica deportiva produce felicidad, el objetivo de este estudio es de averiguar qué variables influyen principalmente en la felicidad del deportista y en concreto, del deportista federado. Una de las novedades de este estudio es que los resultados podrían ayudar a los miembros de las juntas directivas de las federaciones a tomar buenas decisiones y poder contribuir en mayor forma a la felicidad del deportista federado. Las principales variables que encontramos en la literatura que influyen positivamente en la felicidad son la calidad percibida y la satisfacción. A su vez encontramos estudios que confirman la influencia de la confianza y las relaciones sociales sobre la felicidad. El estudio empírico se ha realizado a través de datos primarios mediante encuesta sobre una muestra de 601 individuos federados en las distintas federaciones autonómicas de España, concretamente en la modalidad deportiva de kárate. Los resultados obtenidos confirman todas las hipótesis planteadas en este estudio por lo que como indicaba la literatura revisada las cuatro variables analizadas (la calidad percibida, la satisfacción, la confianza y las relaciones sociales) influyen de forma significativa y positivamente en la felicidad.

Keywords | palabras clave

Happiness, satisfaction, perceived quality, trust, sport, karate, federations, social relationships.
Felicidad, satisfacción, calidad percibida, confianza, deporte, kárate, federaciones, relaciones sociales.

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1. Introduction

Happiness is something people have been looking for since the beginning of time. Achieving the goals is one of the reasons why people experience happiness (Núñez-Barriopedro, Ruiz-López, & Ravina Ripoll, 2018). In this sense, achieving sporting goals can help achieve happiness, so it follows that sport and happiness are closely linked. Sports practice is associated with health. In fact, lack of physical exercise and sedentary is linked to some diseases and disorders (Álvarez, 2007). This is one of the reasons governments promote sport to improve health, fight obesity, curb crime, and provide values to youth (Huang & Humphreys, 2012; Hur, Ko, & Valacich, 2011). Specifically, in Spain [...] “The development of high-level, high-performance sport resides in the Spanish Sports Federations with the collaborations of the Autonomous Communities. It is mainly funded by the State and aims to raise the sporting level of Spain internationally” (Higher Sports Council, 2019, s/p).

The purpose of a sports federation is to promote sport (Supreme Council for Sports in Spain. Ministry of Education, Culture and Sports, 2007), and although they are private organizations, the Public Administration is the one that name and recognize them as an organ for the development of high-level, high-performance sport. Thus, the Administration provides the main economic endowments to these organizations with the aim of raising the sporting level of Spain internationally (Supreme Council for Sports in Spain. Ministry of Education, Culture and Sports, 2007).

Some research has shown that sports consumption as a spectator (Hallmann, Breuer & Ku, 2013; Jang, Ko, Wann & Kim, 2017), sports holidays, attendance at sporting events (Nicolao, Irwin & Goodman, 2009), or participation in events (Huang & Humphreys, 2012; Theodorakis, Kaplanidou & Karabaxoglou, 2015) are closely linked to happiness and increase happiness levels.

Despite the growing public interest in physical activity and sport, there is no perceived proportional growth of members of non-profit sports organizations (Wemmer & Koenigstorfer, 2016). Although over the last 10 years the number of federated licences has remained in a steady number, growth has continued over the last 2 years, but if the timeline is expanded the variation is barely noticeable. Lucrative sports organizations have entered the market with great force and are attracting more and more consumers. However, their nonprofit peers are not standing up for this increase in competition (Smith & Stewart, 2010).

In this context, this paper aims to explore the causes of little variation in licensing over the past 10 years. While it is true that federations are non-profit organizations, their objective is the promotion and dissemination of sport, and this means that one of their main interests is to make their federated happy through sport. Therefore, this work can provide knowledge especially for the members of the boards of the federations in order to know what variables can influence the happiness of their federateds so that they have the opportunity to manage them in the best possible way and, thus, achieve their purpose and mission.

1.1. State-of-the-art

1.1.1. Happiness

Happiness brings a number of sensations, which any mentally healthy person would like to keep as long as possible (Ravina-Ripoll *et al.*, 2019). Some authors define happiness as the positive psychological state derived from a good, pleasant and satisfying experience (Bolifa *et al.*, 2017; Jang *et al.*, 2017). There are two perspectives from which happiness can be analyzed: one alludes to a specific moment in time and the other to a constant duration. The first is the consequence of a particular positive situation or experience, while the second is a general positive psychological state that is cumulative over time (Seligman & Csikszentmihalyi, 2014).

According to numerous studies, happiness and loyalty are positively related. Aksoy *et al.* (2015) empirically confirms that concrete loyalty and abstract loyalty influence happiness. In fact, the optimal balance between them will help maximize overall happiness. Just because the customer is satisfied does not mean that they are happy, but happiness must be sought to bring the customer to loyalty (Khan & Hussain, 2013), rather than focusing on their satisfaction, which is what has been pursued in the last 50 years (Easterlin, 2001).

The quality of life and happiness has been linked many times, and not only that, but when a large part of the population is happy, it will imply that the quality of life of that population is good (Barriopedro, Ripoll, and Tello, 2018a). Happy people tend to have prosperous lives, both externally and internally (Nelson *et al.*, 2015). In the literature on happiness, some researchers argue that a certain person's happiness will depend on a number of factors related to positive feelings, such as social relationships, work and unemployment, leisure, money, class, culture, personality, joy, satisfaction with life, age, sex, health, among others. All this means that the general circumstances of life have an impact on happiness -as a constant construct- (see gr. Argyle, 1994; Barriopedro, Ripoll, and Tello, 2018b; Ravina-Ripoll *et al.*, 2019).

1.1.2. Quality perceived

The most defended definition of perceived quality by the authors refers to discrepancies between consumer perceptions of a particular good or service offered and expectations about such service (v.gr. Hennig-Thurau, Gwinner, & Gremler, 2002; Cuesta Valiño, Gutiérrez Rodríguez, & Núñez-Barriopedro, 2019). In equal perceptions, the higher the consumer expectations, the lower the perceived quality. The conceptual meaning of quality has two dimensions: one mechanical and one humanistic. The mechanical dimension refers to the objective characteristics of the transaction, while the humanistic dimension of quality is relative to the subjective response of people to a certain case and depends on the judgment of each person (Gallarza, *et al.*, 2017).

For the specific case of sports federations, as the product offered are services, customers perceive the exchange relationship with a higher risk. This is due to the main characteristics of the services: intangibility and heterogeneity, reason for which credibility is one of the most important attributes to the consumer when assessing perceived quality (Javalgi & Moberg, 1997).

1.1.3. Satisfaction

Satisfaction can be conceptualized in two ways: satisfaction of a specific transaction and cumulative satisfaction (Boulding *et al.*, 1993), the latter being the general assessment based on the totality of purchases and consumption experiences of a particular good or service (Anderson & Mansi, 2009).

Other authors define it as the customer's emotional or sentimental reaction to perceived differences between job execution and expectations. Although this definition could lead to confusion because of its similarities to the definition of 'perceived quality', the fact is that the two variables are different being the main difference that satisfaction is a type of attitude, long-term assessment; however, perceived quality is the measure of a specific transaction. Núñez-Barriopedro, Ruiz-López, & Ravina Ripoll (2018) relate satisfaction to providing what is being sought to the point that this can be achieved.

1.1.4. Trust

Trust is one of the basic ingredients to succeed in relationships (Cuesta Valiño, Gutiérrez Rodríguez, & Núñez-Barriopedro, 2019), this being the belief of one of the parties that the actions that the other party executes would be satisfying (Anderson & Mansi, 2009).

For its part, trust in an organization is given by the consumer safety in the quality and integrity of the service offered (Hennig-Thurau, Langer, & Hansen, 2001). In the confidence of the relationships between the consumer and companies, the psychological benefit of safety and trust is more relevant than the special relationship or social benefits derived from this relationship (Eaton, Gwinner, Larson & Swanson, 2015). Trust is the involvement in a process that has been well thought out and carefully considered, while affection for a brand is rather spontaneous, more immediate and less reasoned. In this sense, trust can have an affective and cognitive dimension (Johnson & Grayson, 2005).

1.1.5. Relationship between perceived quality and happiness

Improving the quality of service in the purchase of sporting events is an opportunity to positively improve the consumer psychology (Anderson & Mansi, 2009). There are several authors in the literature who demonstrate and confirm the relationship between perceived quality or quality of perceived service and happiness (v.gr. Gong & Yi, 2018; Sato, Jordan & Funk, 2014; Theodorakis *et al.*, 2015).

In their study, Theodorakis *et al.* (2015) try to find out the relationship and the influence of perceived quality and satisfaction on the happiness that the consumption of sporting events can produce. To this end, they build on the statements of Sato, Jordan and Funk (2014), who found that "physically active leisure can improve the quality of life of participants by providing positive experiences through participation in events" (p. 298). As far as sporting events are concerned, Theodorakis *et al.* (2015, op. cit.) mention three types of quality of service: the quality of the results, the quality of interaction and the quality of the physical environment, being the variable of quality of the results the one that influences happiness.

Satisfaction is a variable that is also closely related to perceived quality. It sometimes acts as a mediator variable between it and happiness, as in Gong and Yi's study (2018), in which they measure different perceptions aspects about the overall quality of service such as the environment, development or delivery of the service. These three variables influence satisfaction, which in turn influences loyalty and happiness.

Taking into account the contributions of the revised literature on perceived quality relationships and happiness, the following hypotheses are raised:

H1: Perceived quality positively influences satisfaction

H2: Perceived quality positively influences happiness

1.1.6. Relationship between satisfaction and happiness

Improving the quality of service in the purchase of sporting events is an opportunity to positively improve consumer psychology (Anderson & Mansi, 2009). Happiness and satisfaction with life are two different concepts, but Haller and Hadler (2006) found that macrosocial factors, such as a nation's economic wealth, the distribution of incomes, the state extent of the Welfare, and political freedom influences both happiness and satisfaction. In this sense, when a service occurs repeatedly over the time, perceptions derived from these encounters form the basis of consumer satisfaction and in turn, leading to the consumer happiness (Dagger & Sweeney, 2006).

On the other hand, customer satisfaction extends to any time in life, leading to happiness (Sweeney, Danaher & Mccoll-Kennedy, 2015). This could be related with the bottom-up theory of customer happiness, which states that customer satisfaction, derived from a specific service, extends upwards to the overall satisfaction of the service, and this, in turn extends to happiness (Gong & Yi, 2018). The conclusions obtained from the work analyzed on satisfaction and happiness allowed raising the following hypothesis:

H3: Satisfaction positively influences happiness.

1.1.7. Relationship between confidence and happiness

As observed before improving the quality of service in the purchase of sporting events is an opportunity to positively improve the consumer psychology (Núñez-Barriopedro, Ravina Ripoll, Tobar Pesantez, 2019). The literature that analyzes the relationship between trust and happiness has been studied mainly with data aggregated at the regional or national level (Barra, Pressgrove & Torres, 2018; Bartolini & Mikucka, 2017; Tokuda, Fujii & Inoguchi, 2010), looking for a geographic perspective.

In their research, Bartolini & Mikucka (2017) discuss the relationship between social trust and subjective well-being or happiness in Eastern Europe. For them, trust does not influence happiness in the short term; however, in the medium-long term, the influence of confidence over happiness is equal to the influence of economic growth on happiness. Another study on the relationship between trust and happiness in eastern Japan argues that the relationship between the two variables depends on the context in which they are analyzed (Barra *et al.*, 2018).

Trust can play a very important role in reducing possible negative influences on happiness that can arise when laws do not work well (Barra *et al.*, 2018). People living in

countries with higher levels of aggregate social confidence are more likely to be happy than those living in countries with a poorer level of confidence (Tokuda *et al.*, 2010).

Based on the lines of thought of the revised literature on trust and happiness, the following hypothesis was created:

H4: Trust positively influences happiness

1.1.8. Relationship between social relationships and happiness

Happiness and satisfaction cannot be obtained if social relations or society are set aside (Haller & Hadler, 2006). People have always thought about the structure and social institutions in view of the possibility of achieving a long life and happiness (Boudon, 2002). Haller and Hadler (2006) in their study demonstrate their hypothesis that certain social relationships under some conditions may produce happiness or unhappiness.

Some sports studies show that social relationships influence the happiness of the sports spectator through the identification with the team as a mediating variable: relationships with other fans enhance identification with the team, and the team in turn influences happiness (Jang *et al.*, 2017), as individuals experience greater happiness by participating in activities that facilitate positive and high-quality social connections with others (Haller & Hadler, 2006; Jang *et al.*, 2017). There are several authors who agree that social relations and happiness are intimately related (Romero-Rodríguez & Castillo-Abdul, 2019).

Some authors who investigate how friendship influences happiness discuss various aspects of friendship, such as quality and conflict (v.gr. Demir & Urberg, 2004; Demir & Weitekamp, 2007). Demir and Weitekamp (2007) empirically demonstrate that these two aspects of friendship influence happiness by taking into account two other variables: gender and personality. The following hypothesis is raised by taking into account these lines of thought:

H5: Social relationships positively influence the happiness of exercising.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Sample design

The study was carried out on the population of Spanish sports federations. Sports federations in Spain are organizations that important characteristics since they are private non-profit organizations, although they are collaborators of the Public Administration and sometimes they act as agents of the Public Administration, carrying out the roles of the Public Administration. Sports federations are mixed organizations, having a private and public role at the same time. The main purpose of a sports federation is to promote sport and although they are private organizations, it is the Public Administration that authorizes them as an organ for the development of high-level, high-performance sport. In this sense, the Administration provides the main economic endowments to these organizations with the aim of raising the sport level of Spain internationally. In Spain there are a total of 66 federations, totaling

3.761.498 sports licenses in 2017, while by 2008 the number of federation licenses reached 3,394,384 individuals. It can be observed that there has been an increase in these ten years (367.114), however, the growth line has remained constant over the time, especially considering the population variation in Spain.

The information collected has been obtained from a sample of 601 individuals of which 71% are men and 29% women, all of them federated from the karate sport. In the sample there are individuals of all ages, being the most relevant group the one aging between 45 and 64 years, and in addition most of them have been federated for more than 20 years. Responses were obtained from 11 regional federations, out of a total of 19

Using Google Forms, the self-administered questionnaire was sent to several Spanish regional karate federations for the federated to pass to other federated parties, via a link, using the snowball technique. The Federateds completed the survey during March and April 2019.

3. Analysis and results

According to the ji squared test with 16 degrees of freedom practiced on the sample, it is confirmed for all indicators of the variable quality perceived its relationship with happiness. In addition, in Table 1 is presented the results of the Snedecor F test, which confirms that there are significant differences between the different groups, since the p value is <0.05.

Table 1. Average values of perceived quality indicators according to the happiness degree of the federated

Denomination	Total sample	Participating in the federation's activities makes me happy					F of Snedecor
		Completely Disagree	Disagree	Indifference	Agree	Fully Agree	
The activities of my federation (championships, courses, trainings, etc.) are carried out efficiently.	3.8854	1.9556	2.9149	3.4919	4.1392	4.5044	F(4.597) = 100.8089
	n = 602	n = 45	n = 47	n = 124	n = 158	n = 228	p = 0.0000
My federation provides a pleasant environment to carry out the activities it organizes.	3.9717	1.8444	2.8723	3.6129	4.2468	4.6256	F(4.596) = 141.7542
	n = 601	n = 45	n = 47	n = 124	n = 158	n = 227	p = 0.0000

Denomination	Total sample	Participating in the federation's activities makes me happy					F of Snedecor
		Completely Disagree	Disagree	Indifference	Agree	Fully Agree	
I understand that my federation charges a fair price for the activities in which I participate.	3.9214	2.2045	3	3.3852	4.1329	4.5859	F(4.593) = 82.3918
	n = 598	n = 44	n = 47	n = 122	n = 158	n = 227	p = 0.0000
I am effectively assisted with my inquiries by the employees of my federation.	4.0266	2.2889	3.0851	3.5691	4.2025	4.6886	F(4.596) = 93.4056
	n = 601	n = 45	n = 47	n = 123	n = 158	n = 228	p = 0.0000
The services and activities offered by my federation are really good							

In addition, a test has been carried out to analyze the unidirectional variance between happiness and perceived quality, confirming this approach by rejecting the independence hypothesis of variables, since the result obtained from the F of Snedecor for 4 and 594 degrees of freedom was 155.2908, with an explained variance rate of more than 50%, specifically 51.12%. In Table 2 can be observed the sum of squares for the variables "Participating in the activities of my federation makes me happy" and "The services and activities offered by my federation are really good":

Table 2. Variance analysis of the indicators "Participating in the activities of my federation makes me happy" and "The services and activities offered by my federation are really good"

Groups	Number of Cases	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Sum of squares
Total sample	599	3.7963	1.232	909.1519
Variable relationship categories				
Complete Disagreement	26	1.5	0.9707	24.5
Disagreement	31	2.0968	1.2009	44.7097
Indifference	115	2.9826	1.1032	139.9652
Agree	178	3.8258	0.7989	113.6011
Fully Agree	249	4.6024	0.6989	121.6386
Sum:				444.4146

It can also be mentioned that there is a relationship between all indicators of perceived quality and those of satisfaction, since in all ji squared tests the probability turned out to be 0.000. Likewise, the Snedecor F test indicates that there are significant differences in the mean values of the different cross-tabulations between the indicators of perceived quality and satisfaction.

Both tests, ji squared with 16 degrees of freedom and F of Snedecor have been performed to measure the relationship between the satisfaction of the federated and their happiness. The first test confirms that there is a relationship between the two variables, and the second that there are significant differences between the mean values of the different groups, as can be seen in Table 3.

Table 3. Average values of satisfaction indicators according to the degree of happiness of the federated

Denomination	Total sample	Participating in the federation's activities makes me happy.					F of Snedecor
		Completely Disagree	Disagree	Indifference	Agree	Fully Agree	
I think it is good for me to be federated.	4.5717	3.3556	4.1277	4.3468	4.6815	4.9515	F(4.595) = 61.9795
	n = 600	n = 45	n = 47	n = 124	n = 157	n = 227	p = 0.0000

Denomination	Total sample	Participating in the federation's activities makes me happy.					F of Snedecor
		Completely Disagree	Disagree	Indifference	Agree	Fully Agree	
I am glad to be federated in my federation.	4.1847	2	3.383	3.9113	4.3861	4.793	F(4.596) = 129.0765
	n = 601	n = 45	n = 47	n = 124	n = 158	n = 227	p = 0.0000
I am satisfied with the activities/services offered by my federation.	3.8965	1.8372	2.9362	3.3871	4.0886	4.63	F(4.594) = 130.8788
	n = 599	n = 43	n = 47	n = 124	n = 158	n = 227	p = 0.0000

If carrying out an analysis of the one-way variance taking happiness as a dependent variable on the satisfaction of the athlete, the independence hypothesis is rejected, confirming the hypothesis raised in this study. In addition, the variance percentage explained is close to 50%, with the determination coefficient being 0.4629.

Similarly, looking at the results of both tests on the confidence and happiness variables, it is found that the two variables are related and, in addition, taking into account the results observed in Table 4, there are differences between the different groups of trust and happiness:

Table 4. Average values of confidence indicators according to the degree of happiness of the federated

Denomination	Total sample	Participating in the federation's activities makes me happy.					F of Snedecor
		Completely Disagree	Disagree	Indifference	Agree	Fully Agree	
My federation has behaved the way I expected in the activities in which I have participated.	3.9185	1.9556	2.8936	3.4634	4.1582	4.5965	F(4.596) = 120.7371
	n = 601	n = 45	n = 47	n = 123	n = 158	n = 228	p = 0.0000

Denomination	Total sample	Participating in the federation's activities makes me happy.					F of Snedecor
		Completely Disagree	Disagree	Indifference	Agree	Fully Agree	
My federation is committed to the federated	3.9068	1.7111	2.8298	3.4758	4.1338	4.6404	F(4.596) = 140.9658
	n = 601	n = 45	n = 47	n = 124	n = 157	n = 228	p = 0.0000
My federation is honest with all federated.	3.7663	1.5333	2.8511	3.377	3.8797	4.5286	F(4.594) = 113.3821
	n = 599	n = 45	n = 47	n = 122	n = 158	n = 227	p = 0.0000
My federation cares about the federated	3.7629	1.5778	2.7826	3.2358	3.9557	4.5463	F(4.594) = 130.2304
	n = 599	n = 45	n = 46	n = 123	n = 158	n = 227	p = 0.0000

In relation to the trust, the analysis of variance also rejects the independence hypothesis of this variable with respect to happiness, and also does so with a proportion of the explained variance of 42.85%.

Finally, the study variables related to social relationships are analyzed. The first variable is whether there is a personal relationship with other federated and the second if there are friends in the federation. The ji square tests clearly confirm that both variables are related to the variable "Participating in the activities of the federation makes me happy" and the variable "The Federated are happy when they participate in the activities of my federation."

In Table 5 can be observed the analysis of variances of the happiness variable and the variable "to have a personal relationship with the federated", and it can be observed that the different arithmetic means of each group increase as going from disagreement to agreement. In turn, the F Snedecor test with p-0.0000 confirms that there are significant differences in the arithmetic means of the different groups.

Table 5. One-way variance analysis on the degree of happiness explained by the personal relationship with other federated

Groups	Number of Cases	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Sum of squares
Total sample	599	3.7997	1.2339	911.9599
Variable Relationship categories				
Completely Disagree	34	2.4706	1.3982	66.4706
Disagree	44	2.9091	1.1245	55.6364
Indifference	141	3.3404	1.0969	169.6596
Agree	142	3.7465	1.1097	174.8732
Fully Agree	238	4.458	0.955	217.0798
Sum:				683.7196

In Table 6 is observed the variance analysis that compares the degree of happiness of the federated with the friendship in the federation. The results are very similar to those in the table above, observing the main difference in the determination coefficient, which for table 5 represents a 0.25 while for table 6 a 0.18.

Table 6. One-way variance analysis on the degree of happiness explained by friendship in the federation

Groups	Number of Cases	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Sum of squares
Total sample	598	3.796	1.2303	905.1104
Variable Relationship categories				
Completely Disagree	18	2.1111	1.2862	29.7778
Disagree	16	3.1875	1.1842	22.4375
Indifference	73	3.1644	1.1349	94.0274
Agree	127	3.3701	1.0781	147.6063
Fully Agree	364	4.1813	1.1094	448.033
Sum:				741.8819

Discussion and conclusions

The results of this study are conclusive, as all the evidence carried out on the sample obtained leads to the confirmation of the hypotheses raised in the preceding paragraphs.

In analyzing the variable of perceived quality is obtained that the perceived quality influences the happiness of the Spanish federated athlete using satisfaction as a mediator variable both directly and indirectly (*H1*). Therefore, in this case, the

empirical study would confirm the revised works on the theory of perceived quality and happiness (Gong & Yi, 2018; Sato *et al.*, 2014; Theodorakis *et al.*, 2015).

The results also indicate that satisfaction and happiness have a strong relationship and not only that, but that the hypothesis (H2) raised after the bibliographic review is confirmed, having a powerful influence on the happiness of the federated (H3), being in agreement with the authors reviewed (Dagger & Sweeney, 2006; Gong & Yi, 2018; Haller & Hadler, 2006; Sweeney *et al.*, 2015).

With regard to the variable confidence, although the study of its influence on happiness is not as broad in the literature as that of the previous two variables, there are several authors who argue that both variables are related and that happiness is affected by the degree of trust in the organization (Barra *et al.*, 2018; Bartolini & Mikucka, 2017; Tokuda *et al.*, 2010), and the results of the study analyzed agree with these authors, since the hypothesis raised about the positive influence of confidence on happiness is clearly confirmed (H4).

The last hypothesis raised (H5), which studies the relationship between social relations and the happiness that sports activity has is conclusive, since all statisticians clearly confirm the hypothesis that social relations influence in the happiness derived from sport. Therefore, it is clear that for Spanish karate federated, having a personal relationship with their peers or having a friendship provide them more happiness. This corresponds to the information revised in the literature, since for many authors social relations in general (Boudon, 2002; Gilbert, 2005; Haller & Hadler, 2006) as friendship (Jang *et al.*, 2017) influence people's happiness.

For the managers of the federations, the recommendations following the results derived from this research are to maximize as much as possible the quality of their services since this variable has a greater explanation than the rest of the variables, in addition to the influence not only on happiness but the satisfaction of the federated (Gong & Yi, 2018). This without forgetting the importance of the variable confidence, since the existence of trust on the part of the federation helps to maintain happiness in times when there is not the best service or the best results (Barra *et al.*, 2018; Tokuda *et al.*, 2010). Last but not least, it must be remembered that strengthening social relations among all people who participate in the federation, motivating friendship and companionship will be another key piece to keep the federated happy (Haller & Hadler, 2006).

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